
Development of Processing–Microstructure–Mechanical Behavior Paradigms for Tungsten Heavy Alloys

*A thesis submitted in fulfilment of the requirements
for the degree of Master of Technology*

by

Mirtunjay Kumar

DEPARTMENT OF MATERIALS SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY KANPUR

February 2019

Certificate

It is certified that the work contained in this thesis entitled “**Development of Processing–Microstructure–Mechanical Behavior Paradigms for Tungsten Heavy Alloys**” by **Mirtunjay Kumar** has been carried out under my supervision and that it has not been submitted elsewhere for a degree.

A. Upadhyaya
4.2.19

Prof. Anish Upadhyaya

Professor

MSE Department

Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur

NP Gurao
04/02/19

Prof. Nilesh Prakash Gurao

Associate Professor

MSE Department

Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur

Declaration

This is to certify that the thesis titled “**Development of Processing–Microstructure–Mechanical Behavior Paradigms for Tungsten Heavy Alloys**” has been authored by me. It presents the research conducted by me under the supervision of **Prof. Anish Upadhyaya** and **Prof. Nilesh Prakash Gurao**.

To the best of my knowledge, it is an original work, both in terms of research content and narrative, and has not been submitted elsewhere, in part or in full, for a degree. Further, due credit has been attributed to the relevant state-of-the-art and collaborations with appropriate citations and acknowledgments, in line with established norms and practices.

Mirtunjay Kumar

Roll No. 14206261

MSE Department

Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur

Abstract

Name of the student: **Mirtunjay Kumar**

Roll No: **14206261**

Degree for which submitted: **MTech**

Department: **MSE Department**

Thesis title: **Development of Processing–Microstructure–Mechanical Behavior Paradigms for Tungsten Heavy Alloys**

Thesis supervisors: **Prof. Anish Upadhyaya** and **Prof. Nilesh Prakash Gurao**

Month and year of thesis submission: **February 2019**

Tungsten heavy alloy (WHA) is manufactured using liquid phase sintering for use in electrical, radiation, inertial, ordnance, or structural components. WHA is made up primarily of tungsten (typically 90 wt% or greater) grains that are dispersed in a matrix of two or more different elements that can be selected from Fe, Ni, Co, and Cu. Various metal-working processes and heat treatment cycles are used to improve the properties of these materials, but the near-net shape is sacrificed in the process. The traditional method of sintering has proven difficult to implement and has not been investigated in detail. In this study, an effort was made to achieve full density by conventional sintering while maintaining an excellent combination of dimensional stability and required strength. This was done by using conventional sintering as the sole processing technique. The goal that was set out to achieve was successfully attained through careful manipulation of the matrix content and sintering parameters. Changes in microstructural characteristics, such as grain growth, contiguity, and connectivity, were also investigated as a function of sintering time. The microstructural quantities of sintered alloys were quantified using EBSD, and the hardness, tensile and compressive strength of these alloys were evaluated. The tensile and compressive strengths were discovered to be sensitive to the strain rate. In order to quantify the sensitivity, the strain rate jump test was carried out, and the activation

volume that was associated with it was derived. The hardness variation with deformation was observed and found to conform to the voce hardening law trend. On the fracture surface of the tensile sample, investigation was also conducted that looked at a different mode of failure.

Acknowledgements

The completion of this thesis would not have been possible without the support and encouragement of several special people. Hence, I would like to take this opportunity to show my gratitude to those who have assisted me in a myriad of ways. I acknowledge with extreme gratitude the professional supervision from Dr. A. Upadhyaya and Dr. N. P. Gurao for his expert guidance, support and encouragement throughout my post graduate study at Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur. Their dynamic personality and positive attitude will be the source of inspiration throughout my career. I would like to thank Prof. Monica Katiyar (present head of department), Prof. Anish Upadhyaya and Prof. Sandeep Sangal (previous head of department) for providing excellent research facility in the department. I am extremely grateful to Prof. Gouthama and Prof. Shashank Shekhar for allowing me independent usage of characterization facilities in advance center for materials science (ACMS), IIT Kanpur. I express my deep gratitude to Dr. Manasij Yadava for his time to time guidance in the completion of present thesis work. I extend my special thanks to Mr. Sheelendra Agnihotri and Mr. Udham Singh for his necessary help during my experimental work. I am extremely grateful to all staff members of Department of Material Science and Engineering and ACMS for their kind cooperation and assistance during my research work. My Special thanks are dedicated to Mr. Surendra Agnihotri, Mr. G.P. Bajpai, Mr. Anil Verma and Mrs. Samata Samal for kindly allowing me to utilize facilities at TA-201 lab, Departmental workshop and Material testing lab. I would like to acknowledge Mr. Siva kumar, Mr. D.D. Pal, Mr. Ashish, Mr. Jai Kishan, Mr. Kamlesh Thapliyal and Mr. Rupesh Kumar Sharma for helping me in carrying out several important experiments in ACMS. I would like to take opportunity to thank my all lab mates Dr. M. Ashiq, Dr. Satish Kanhed, Dr. Sumeet Mishra, Dr. Subhashish Sinha, Mr. Roopam Jain, Mr. Vivek Sahu, Ms. Reshma Sonkusare, Mr. Satish Kaithal, Mr. Subhamay Biswas, Mr. Kapil Verma, Mr. Mahesh Paidapilli, Mr. Avinash Singh, Mr. Kumar Debajyoti Jena, Mr. Harish Ranot, Mr. Felege N., Mr. Navindra Shekhar Shakunt and Mr. Prasanna for their encouragement and help at every possible step. I thank all my friends for their support and companionship who made my stay at IIT Kanpur very pleasant and memorable. I am grateful to my friends for their love and affection and I wish them all success in their life. Last but not the least, I thank my parents, sister and brother for providing me their moral support, motivation and encouragement.

Contents

Acknowledgements	vi
List of Figures	x
List of Tables	xii
Abbreviations	xiii
Symbols	xiv
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Introduction to tungsten heavy alloy	1
1.2 Objective of the work	3
1.3 Scope and organization of the thesis	3
2 Literature Review	5
2.1 Brief introduction to heavy alloy	5
2.2 Application of Tungsten Alloys	6
2.3 Background	7
2.3.1 Early Work	7
2.3.2 Research work related to W–Ni–Fe	7
2.4 Physical chemistry of WHA	9
2.4.1 Related phase diagram	10
2.4.2 Sintering	12
2.4.3 Solid state sintering	12
2.4.4 Liquid phase sintering	13
2.4.5 Densification during sintering	16
2.4.6 Solution-precipitation process	19
2.4.7 Densification mechanism during solution reprecipitation	20
2.4.8 Neck growth	22
2.4.9 Coalescence	24

2.4.10	Mechanism of Coalescence	25
2.4.11	Grain Coarsening	26
2.4.12	Pore filling	27
2.4.13	Research work related to sintering of heavy alloy	27
2.5	Mechanical property of WHA	29
2.5.1	Mushrooming effect	29
3	Materials and Methods	32
3.1	Materials	32
3.2	Powder Characterization	32
3.2.1	Particle Size and its distribution	32
3.2.2	Particle shape	33
3.3	Sample preparation	33
3.4	Compaction	34
3.5	Sintering	34
3.6	Different sintering cycle	34
3.7	Density measurement	35
3.8	Metallographic Sample Preparation	36
3.8.1	Sample Selection	36
3.9	Matrix volume optimisation	37
3.10	Sintering time optimisation	38
3.11	Mechanical characterisation	38
3.11.1	Vickers Macro hardness	38
3.11.2	Vickers Microhardness	38
3.11.3	Compression test	39
3.11.4	Tensile test	39
3.12	Electron Backscattered diffraction	39
3.13	Quantitative Metallography	39
3.13.1	Microstructure evolution	39
3.13.2	Contiguity of the microstructural surface	40
3.13.3	Connectivity	40
3.13.4	Dihedral angle	40
3.13.5	Grain size measurement	42
4	Results and Discussion	43
4.1	Experimental Results	43
4.1.1	Powder Characterization	43
4.2	Effect of presintering	44
4.3	Density and densification behavior	44
4.4	Matrix fraction optimization	46
4.5	Optical Micrographs	46
4.6	Stereological studies	46
4.6.1	Contiguity	46
4.6.2	Connectivity	48

4.6.3	Dihedral angle	48
4.7	Effect of sintering time	49
4.7.1	Grain size distribution	49
4.7.2	Dihedral angle	50
4.7.3	3D Co-ordination number	50
4.7.4	Connectivity	50
4.8	EBSD	52
4.9	Mechanical behaviour	54
4.9.1	Effect of strain rate on Yield strength	54
4.10	Fractography	58
5	Summary and Conclusions	59
	Bibliography	61

List of Figures

2.1	Microstructure of (a) Solid state sintered [1] and (b) Liquid phase sintered of 90W-7Ni-3Fe [2]	10
2.2	Fe–Ni phase diagram [3]	11
2.3	Ni–W phase diagram [3]	12
2.4	Fe–W phase diagram [3]	13
2.5	W–Ni–Fe ternary isotherm [4]	14
2.6	Schematic diagram of solid-state sintering showing the formation of open pore and close pore during sintering	14
2.7	Schematic of the microstructure changes during liquid phase sintering facilitating grain growth and pore removal	15
2.8	A schematic diagram showing the particle fragmentation and rearrangement	15
2.9	Ideal phase diagram that gives solid solubility in the liquid with a low solubility of the liquid in the solid	16
2.10	A schematic of the overlapping events in LPS	17
2.11	Schematic showing low and high contact angle	18
2.12	Schematic showing large and small particles at the start of liquid phase sintering	19
2.13	Schematic showing reprecipitation of tungsten after liquid phase sintering	20
2.14	Schematic showing three mechanisms of grain shape accommodation in LPS (a) Contact flattening (b) Small grain dissolution (c) Solid state bonding for neck formation	21
2.15	Schematic showing two spherical particles with grain diameter G forming bond of length X	24
2.16	Schematic showing coalescence during LPS of different size	24
2.17	Schematic showing radius of curvature of grain boundary depends on dihedral angle and the grain size ratio $\frac{G_1}{G_2}$	25
2.18	Schematic showing the mechanisms of coalescence during LPS (a) Solid state grain boundary motion (b) Liquid film migration (c) solution reprecipitation (d) small grain rotation to a lattice coincidence orientation where there is no grain boundary	26
2.19	Schematic showing pore filling in LPS	28
2.20	Penetrator deformation behavior of (a) Depleted Uranium and (b) WHA penetrator	30
3.1	Micrograph of (a) Tungsten powder (b) Iron powder (c) Nickel powder	33
3.2	Presence of porosity and blisters after the three-step cycle	34

3.3	Absence of porosity and blister after adopting the pre-sintering treatment at 1000 °C for 30 min.	35
3.4	Sintering profile of a) Three step sintering b) sintering profile with pre-sintering treatment	35
3.5	Representation of steps in image processing (a) typical WHA micrograph (b) segmentation of micrograph to different class (c) binary image (d) edge detection	41
3.6	(a) Graph showing detection of entrant corners (negative curvature values) and (b) determination of angle by fitting points near corner	41
4.1	Micrograph of pre-sintered tungsten heavy alloy	44
4.2	Relative density of green compacts and sintered compacts vs matrix content	45
4.3	Densification parameter of WHA sintered sample with matrix content	45
4.4	Photos of the WHAs after sintering at 1500°C for 30 min with initial green porosity of ~54%	46
4.5	Optical micrograph of (a) 98W-1.4Ni-0.6Fe (b) 95W-3.5Ni-1.5Fe (c) 90W-7Ni-3Fe (d) 85W-10.5Ni-4.5Fe and (e)80W-14Ni-6Fe	47
4.6	Plot of (a) Contiguity and (b) Connectivity as a function of matrix content sintered at 1500 °C	48
4.7	Variation of dihedral angle in WHA with matrix content sintered at 1500 °C	49
4.8	Plot of tungsten grain size vs sintering time at temperature 1500 °C	50
4.9	Plot showing the variation of aspect ratio of tungsten grain with sintering time at 1500 °C	51
4.10	Plot showing the distribution of tungsten grain size with varying sintering time sintered at 1500 °C	51
4.11	Stereographic triangle, each color indicating an individual orientation	52
4.12	Inverse pole figure map of powder particle showing single orientation in each powder particle	52
4.13	Inverse pole figure map of as sinter sample showing tungsten embedded in large grain of matrix	53
4.14	Inverse pole figure map of powder particle showing single orientation in each powder particle	53
4.15	Plot showing the compressive stress-strain curve at different strain rates	54
4.16	Plot of hardness variation at different strain when compressed at strain rate of $0.025 s^{-1}$	55
4.17	Plot showing the tensile stress-strain curve at different strain rate	55
4.18	Plot showing the strain rate jump test in tensile mode showing the strain rate jump from $0.1s^{-1}$ to $0.001 s^{-1}$ and finally to $1 s^{-1}$	56
4.19	Fractograph showing the secondary crack in W grain and W/W debonding	56
4.20	Fractograph of WHA showing the W/M debonding failure	57
4.21	Fractograph of WHA showing the matrix tearing as one of failure mechanism	57

List of Tables

3.1	Particle size distribution of elemental powder	33
3.2	Metallographic sample preparation	37
4.1	Characteristics of the as-received powders	43

Abbreviations

EBSD	Electron backscatter diffraction
BSE	Back scattered electron
WHA	Tungsten heavy alloys
P/M	Powder metallurgy
LPS	Liquid phase sintering
f.c.c.	face centred cubic
b.c.c.	body centred cubic
UTS	ultimate tensile strength

Symbols

C_g contiguity

ϕ_d Dihedral angle

“Dedicated to the memory of MY FATHER”

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Introduction to tungsten heavy alloy

Tungsten heavy alloys (WHA) is an pseudo-alloy of tungsten, nickel, and iron [5]. These materials are known for their high density, excellent strength and wear resistance, and good radiation shielding properties. They are used in a variety of applications, including in the aerospace and defense industries, as well as in the medical field [6, 7, 8]. The sintering process is a key step in the manufacturing of tungsten heavy alloys. It involves the heating of tungsten powder and transient metals to a temperature below their melting point, in order to bond the particles together and form a solid mass. This process is typically carried out in a tubular sintering furnace, which can be either a batch or continuous type [9, 10]. There are several steps involved in the sintering process for tungsten heavy alloys [2, 11]:

1. Mixing and compaction: The tungsten powder and other materials are mixed together and then compacted using a press or other mechanical means to form a green body.
2. Drying: The green body is then dried to remove any remaining moisture.
3. Pre-sintering: The green body is then heated to a temperature that is slightly below its melting point, in order to remove any remaining binders and to promote the bonding of the particles.
4. Final sintering: The green body is then heated to its final sintering temperature, which is typically in the range of 1300-1400 °C. At this temperature, the tungsten particles will bond together to form a solid mass.
5. Cooling: After sintering, the tungsten heavy alloy is allowed to cool slowly in order to prevent any stress or strain on the material.

The sintering process is important for the manufacturing of tungsten heavy alloys because it allows the tungsten particles to be bonded together in a way that maximizes their strength and wear resistance. It is also a cost-effective method for producing these materials, as it allows for the production of large quantities of tungsten heavy alloys with a high level of consistency.

These two-phase alloys contain more than 85 wt% near-spherical tungsten particles embedded in a ductile matrix, and are manufactured by combining tungsten, a dense, strong, and highly conductive metal, with other elements to impart it with specific properties and applications [8]. There are mainly three types of applications of tungsten heavy alloy (a) when weight and compact size are important, such as in the manufacture of counterweights, balance weights, and radiation shielding, (b) when a balance of density and strength is required, such as in the aerospace and defense industries, (c) when good machinability are important, such as in the manufacturing of electrical contacts and other electrical components. These alloys are blessed with unique combination of properties such as high density (17–19 g/cm³), low coefficient of thermal expansion, good radiation resistance, excellent mechanical strength, high resistance to deformation and creep at high temperatures, high machinability and high electrical and thermal conductivity [12, 13]. Even though most of the properties of tungsten alloys are known, there are several reasons why researchers are still investigating tungsten heavy alloys:

1. Continued development: While tungsten heavy alloys have many useful properties, there is still room for improvement. Researchers are working to develop new alloys or to modify the composition of existing alloys in order to optimize their properties for specific applications.
2. New applications: Researchers are also studying tungsten heavy alloys in order to find new applications for these materials. For example, they may be looking at how tungsten heavy alloys can be used in new industries, or how they can be used in new and innovative ways within existing industries.
3. Improved manufacturing processes: Researchers are also studying tungsten heavy alloys in order to improve the manufacturing processes used to produce these materials. This may involve finding new ways to mix and compact the materials, or developing new sintering techniques to improve the quality and consistency of the final product.
4. Advanced characterization techniques: Researchers are also using advanced characterization techniques, such as microscopy and spectroscopy, to study tungsten heavy alloys at the micro and nanoscale. This allows them to better understand the properties and behavior of these materials, and to identify potential areas for improvement.

Overall, there are many different reasons why researchers are still investigating tungsten

heavy alloys, and their work is helping to advance our understanding of these materials and to find new and innovative uses for them.

1.2 Objective of the work

This work deals the W–Ni–Fe system with pressure-less conventional sintering and expect to achieve the following goal.

1. To understand the role of sintering profile in pressure-less conventional sintering.
2. To optimize the maximum volume of liquid content.
3. To study the grain growth kinetics and stereological analysis.
4. To develop an algorithm and automatic measurement of dihedral angle.
5. To comprehend the mechanical behavior of optimized W–Ni–Fe alloy system.

1.3 Scope and organization of the thesis

The scope of this thesis is to study the microstructural evolution and mechanical properties of W–Ni–Fe based tungsten heavy alloys during the conventional sintering process. In this work, a series of tungsten heavy alloys with different compositions will be prepared using powder metallurgy techniques, and the sintering behavior of these materials will be studied using a combination of experimental methods. The goal of this research is to gain a deeper understanding of the factors that influence the microstructural evolution and mechanical properties of tungsten heavy alloys, and to identify strategies for optimizing the development of W–Ni–Fe alloy from conventional sintering. The results of this study will have significant implications for the design and manufacture of tungsten heavy alloys, and will contribute to the development of new and improved materials for use in a variety of applications. [Chapter 2](#) consists of literature survey as it allows us to gain an understanding of the existing knowledge and research. It starts with introduction about WHA, Powder metallurgy (P/M) processing of W–Ni–Fe alloys, mechanical working, mechanical properties relating to thermomechanical processing. Different aspects of microstructural characterization by stereology, grain growth kinetics and mechanical testing has also been discussed. The identified gap in the current knowledge has been outlined. The [Chapter 3](#) describes the detail of experimental procedures adapted during the research work. To

ensure the reproducibility of the research, a thorough procedure has been included such as powder characterization, sintering procedures, sample preparation, density measurement, hardness measurement, compression test, tensile test and quantitative analysis of microstructure through stereology for volume fraction, surface to volume fraction measurements, connectivity, contiguity and dihedral angle determination. [Chapter 4](#) deals with the experimental results and subsequently [Chapter 5](#) consists of discussion and conclusion.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2.1 Brief introduction to heavy alloy

In the past four decades, there has been an increase in the amount of research and development that is conducted on WHA. This can be attributed to the wide variety of physical and mechanical properties that WHA possess. These alloys find application in a diverse set of fields, ranging from the medical to the defense industries. WHA are an excellent choice for use as components of collimators and shields, as well as for weight balance, damping, and penetrators of kinetic energy [10, 9]. The microstructure of a typical WHA consists of grains of pure body centred cubic (b.c.c.) tungsten with a globular shape, and these grains are surrounded by a phase of nickel alloy that is relatively soft and ductile [14]. The matrix phase are solid solution of transition metals such as iron, nickel, and tungsten. Heavy alloys are typically processed through the P/M route due to the presence of tungsten as one of the major constituents. The process known as Liquid phase sintering (LPS) is typically used to produce products with full densities. Due to eutectic reaction, alloying elements like Ni and Fe initially melt at relatively low temperatures. It can be seen from the ternary phase diagram of W–Ni–Fe that the eutectic liquid phase is formed at a temperature of 1465 °C [15]. Consequently, the typical sintering temperature range for WHA is 1450–1500 °C. The melt is produced through a eutectic reaction, which wets the tungsten particles by causing capillary action and diffusion around them. The melt that was formed has also dissolves some of the tungsten that was present. The LPS method produces a microstructure that is characterized by nearly spherical grains of tungsten that range in size from 20 to 40 μm and a continuous Ni solid solution matrix phase that is dispersed throughout the alloy [16].

2.2 Application of Tungsten Alloys

WHA is known for their high density, excellent strength and wear resistance, and good radiation shielding properties, which make them suitable for a wide variety of applications in different industries.

Some of the industries that use tungsten heavy alloys include [17, 18, 19, 20, 21]:

1. Aerospace and defense: Tungsten heavy alloys are used in the aerospace and defense industries for applications such as counterweights in aircraft and missiles, and ballast in ships.
2. Medical: Tungsten heavy alloys are used in the medical field for applications such as radiation shielding in cancer treatment, and in the manufacture of surgical instruments and implants.
3. Oil and gas: Tungsten heavy alloys are used in the oil and gas industry for applications such as downhole drilling tools and wellhead components.
4. Construction: Tungsten heavy alloys are used in the construction industry for applications such as radiation shielding walls and doors, and in the manufacture of counterweights for cranes and other heavy machinery.
5. Manufacturing: Tungsten heavy alloys are also used in the manufacturing industry for applications such as electrical contacts, bearings, and high-temperature coatings.
6. These are also used for high temperature applications due to its ability to maintain its strength at higher temperatures and its high fusion point. These applications include the filaments of light bulbs, electron beam tubes, and thermionic vacuum tubes, as well as heating components, rocket nozzles, plasma-facing materials, penetrators in ordnance applications, and fastening applications.
7. Thin film technology uses these alloys due to its low thermal expansion coefficient and high electrical conductivity. Integrated circuits make use of it as an interconnect material because of the low diffusivity it has to the layers that are adjacent to it. It has a high conduction rate and is relatively chemically inert, so electron beam instruments make use of it in both the electrodes and the emitter tips of the devices.

Overall, tungsten heavy alloys are used in a wide variety of industries and applications due to their unique combination of properties, which make them suitable for a range of demanding and specialized uses.

2.3 Background

2.3.1 Early Work

In 1935, McLennan and Smithells [22] reported the development of a W–Ni–Cu alloy containing approximately 90% tungsten and produced by LPS elemental powders at ~ 1400 °C. Further investigations into this system were carried out by Price, *et al.* [23]. They described the structure of W–Ni–Cu alloys of various compositions and produced at different sintering temperatures. Those sintered at temperatures high enough to form a liquid phase ($T > 1350$ °C) were found to consist of large rounded grains of tungsten embedded in a tungsten-saturated Ni–Cu–W matrix. For alloys with $< 90\%$ W, near theoretical density was obtained. Green, *et al.* [24] were first to produce W–Ni–Fe heavy alloys and employed the same procedure used for the W–Ni–Cu alloys. They measured the properties of a series of alloys containing 75–97 wt.% tungsten with the Ni/Fe ratio maintained constant at 7:3. This choice of Ni/Fe ratio can be understood by observation of the Ni–Fe phase equilibrium diagram [25]. A minimum in the liquidus occurs at 1436 °C with composition $\sim 68\text{Ni}–32\text{Fe}$. The authors assumed that this feature would be maintained in the ternary Ni–Fe–W so that the liquid phase would solidify without coring developing in the γ -phase [25].

In the last 25 years the majority of heavy alloy research has been concerned with the W–Ni–Fe system. The reason for this emphasis is that W–Ni–Fe alloys have generally been found to have superior mechanical properties (particularly tensile elongation) to the W–Ni–Cu alloys [26]. Additionally, researchers have tended to maintain the Ni/Fe ratio in the range of 1:1 to 7:3. Partly this was to avoid γ -phase coring, as mentioned previously, but it was also done to prevent the formation of undesirable intermetallic compounds. For example, if the heavy alloy was produced with a very high Ni/Fe ratio, the intermetallic Ni_4W could be formed. Likewise, if the Ni/Fe ratio was too low, the μ -phase (Fe_7W_6) would be produced. The presence of either intermetallic has been associated with alloy embrittlement, and therefore appropriate nickel and iron concentrations have been chosen to avoid their occurrence [27].

2.3.2 Research work related to W–Ni–Fe

Dzykovich *et al.* [28] studied the distribution of elements in W–Ni–Fe system and demonstrated that addition of iron to these alloys affects the mutual solubility of tungsten and

nickel. Minakova *et al.* [29] investigated the structural changes taking place in W–Ni–Fe alloys during slow cooling from the sintering temperature and showed that aging occurs in the binder phase and in a layer of the refractory tungsten-base phase adjoining the low-melting-point constituent. They also established that the change in the mechanism of rupture from brittle to tough is due to structural changes in the alloy linked with the aging process. Agababova and Chaporova [30] studied the boundary of the monophasic γ -solid solution region. Alloys containing 80% Ni and 20% Fe are characterized by the highest solubility of tungsten in the (Ni, Fe) W γ -solid solution, and this solubility varies little with temperature. Zukas and Levinson [31] showed the matrix motion of low-volume matrix W–Ni–Fe composites sintered in a temperature gradient and showed that spheroid growth behavior cannot be predicted reliably from results obtained by sintering in a temperature gradient. German and Churn [32] examined the role of sintering atmosphere in stabilizing detrimental residual pore structures. It was also discussed that prolonged sintering is attributed to pore coarsening. Upadhyaya *et al.* [6], Mondal *et al.* [33], Liu *et al.* [34], Zhou *et al.* [35] compared the effect of heating mode (conventional vs microwave) on the microstructure and mechanical properties of this system and reported that microwave sintering results in better mechanical properties. Clayton [36] presents the constitutive framework for modeling the dynamic response of heavy alloy system and discuss the aspects associated with constitutive modeling of damage and failure in the homogenized material system. Kipphut *et al.* [37] discuss the gravity and configurational energy induced microstructural changes in LPS and thereby improves the understanding of microstructure, mechanical properties, component shape, and dimensional stability in heavy alloy system. Churn and German [38] studied the fracture behavior of W–Ni–Fe system, it was shown that initial cracking occurs at the tungsten-tungsten grain boundaries and in the tungsten grain and latter crack propagate to give eventual failure. The ductility to failure is governed by the strength of the tungsten-matrix interface. The maximum elongation depends on the contiguity which in turn is set by composition. Edmonds and Jones [39] studied the variations in toughness of the liquid-phase sintered heavy alloys W–Ni–Fe and W–Ni–Cu. Toughness was found to be controlled primarily by the strength of the tungsten particle-matrix interfaces and transmission electron microscopy identified interfacial precipitation of a W(NiFe) intermetallic compound. Ramesh and Coates [40] studies the microstructural influence on the dynamic response of WHA. They illustrated that rate-hardening mechanism within the composite appears to be essentially that associated with the tungsten grains; however, the matrix contribution is significant in the case of an undeformed alloy. Humail *et al.* [41] and Hong and Ryu [42] showed the dependence of mechanical property on microstructural attributes such as tungsten particle size,

matrix volume fraction and tungsten/tungsten contiguity which are controllable through the two-stage sintering process. Bose and German [43] investigated the effect of sintering atmosphere on the tensile property of heavy alloys and in other experiment it was also shown that additions like vanadium, niobium, and chromium improves the sintered strengths. The strengthening effect comes from both the solid solution alloying and microstructure control aspects associated with these additions. It was also revealed that long time vacuum sintering leads to property degradation due to preferential matrix vaporization. Park *et al.* [44] studied the microstructural changes during LPS, they demonstrated that skeleton of grains is already formed prior to liquid formation irrelevant starting powder is fine or coarse. During the isothermal LPS, substantial grain growth occurs, and the liquid flows into both open and closed pores, filling them sequentially from the regions with small cross-sections. The grains subsequently grow, into, the liquid pockets which have been formed at the pore sites. The sequential pore filling by first liquid thus is shown to be the dominant densification process during the LPS of this alloy. Olevsky *et al.* [45] shows the shape distortion during LPS due to gravity. Zhou and Clifton [46], Shawki *et al.* [47] observed the shear bands in the impact experiments indicating intense localized deformation. Eventual failure is the combination of grain-matrix separation, ductile matrix rupture, and grain fracture.

2.4 Physical chemistry of WHA

WHA are two-phase alloys, based on primarily W–Ni–Fe and W–Ni–Cu. Although, tungsten based sintered heavy alloys with Cu–Ni binder were initially developed, attention was eventually diverted to Fe–Ni binder because of better attained mechanical properties. WHA based on the W–Ni–Fe are a class of alloys characterised by high density [48]. These alloys are processed by sintering, namely solid-state sintering and LPS from elemental powder mixes where tungsten ranges from 80 to 98 weight percent. It is quite difficult to achieve full density through solid-state sintering, so LPS is commonly used to consolidate these alloys. The final liquid phase sintered alloy consists of nearly pure tungsten grains dispersed in a ductile matrix. The typical microstructures of solid-state sintered and liquid phase sintered are shown in Figure 2.1.

The mean tungsten grain size varies from 15–60 μm depending on initial particle size, the volume fraction of tungsten, sintering temperature and time. These alloys have the best combination of optimal mechanical properties and cost effectiveness among all tungsten

FIGURE 2.1: Microstructure of (a) Solid state sintered [1] and (b) Liquid phase sintered of 90W-7Ni-3Fe [2]

base heavy alloys. The desirable combination of density (16–18 g/cm³), ductility (10–30%), strength (1000–1700 MPa), conductivity, machinability and corrosion resistance make WHA composites unique in the spectrum of materials. Other tungsten based heavy alloys are W–Cu–Ni, W–Co–Ni, and W–Cr–Ni. W–Co–Ni alloys are costly due to the binder constituents. Moreover, some of these alloys particularly, Co based WHA are susceptible to the precipitation of intermetallic phase such as W–Co₇ [49]. Uhrenius *et al.* [50] have reported that nickel binder proved to be better as compared to the binary Co–Ni binders as far as the mechanical properties were concerned. The W–Cr–Ni alloy exhibit higher ultimate tensile strength along with poor ductility values. The presence of brittle phase makes it suitable for high hardness applications [51].

2.4.1 Related phase diagram

W–Ni–Fe alloy exhibit excellent combination of ductility and strength and can be cold worked to a reduction of 70% without intermediate annealing. Higher addition of iron causes a significant matrix strengthening effect and improves high-temperature strength.

As shown in Figure 2.2, it is clear that Ni–Fe having a ratio of 7:3 have a melting point about 1440 °C. The phase diagram of Ni–W and W–Fe is given in Figure 2.3 and Figure 2.4 respectively. Figure 2.5 shows the ternary phase diagram of W–Ni–Fe alloy. In W–Ni–Fe heavy alloy, matrix consists about 22–25% dissolved tungsten depending upon the process parameters. The equilibrium phase diagram shows that in this composition matrix will exist in γ (face centred cubic (f.c.c.)) form. For W–Ni–Fe system, it has been observed that a eutectic melt of Ni–Fe forms at 1435 °C, but in practice, due to inhomogeneous

FIGURE 2.2: Fe–Ni phase diagram [3]

mixing of powders the melt formation occurs at slightly higher temperature (1465 °C). In W–Ni–Fe system, tungsten grains are embedded in the ductile Ni–Fe matrix.

The formation of different intermetallics depends on Ni to Fe ratio in the system. It is minimum when the nickel to iron ratio is 7:3. Nickel to iron ratio plays an important role in the selection of W–Ni–Fe alloys for specific applications. Typically, Ni to Fe ratio ranges between 1:1 and 4:1. Various research has been done to study the mechanical property of WHA by varying the ratio between the Ni and Fe [26, 52, 53, 54, 55]. Mechanical properties of as sintered alloy depends upon the Ni:Fe ratio, the most important factor that should be considered for selection is to avoid the formation of brittle intermetallic phases at the tungsten–matrix interface. Among the various Ni to Fe ratios studied, 7:3 and 8:2 are frequently used, with a large number of investigations using 7:3. The selection of Ni to Fe ratio of 7:3 effectively prevents the formation of brittle intermetallic phases. Caldwell [56] has shown that it is possible to use higher or lower Ni to Fe ratio to achieve similar mechanical properties by using proper heat treatment. Ni to Fe ratio higher than either 7:3 or 8:2 can significantly improve mechanical properties if proper heat treatment is performed to control the precipitation of brittle intermetallic phases.

FIGURE 2.3: Ni-W phase diagram [3]

2.4.2 Sintering

Sintering phenomena in the solid-state takes place during heating a powder up to the temperature for LPS. The driving force for solid-state sintering is excess surface free energy. Figure 2.6 schematically represents the different stages involved in solid state sintering. Sintering is a complex process and for any given metal and set of sintering conditions there are likely to be different stages and material transport mechanisms associated with this process [57].

2.4.3 Solid state sintering

Sintering phenomena in the solid-state takes place during heating a powder up to the temperature for LPS. The driving force for solid-state sintering is excess surface free energy. Figure 2.6 schematically represents the different stages involved in solid state sintering. Sintering is a complex process and for any given metal and set of sintering conditions there

FIGURE 2.4: Fe-W phase diagram [3]

are likely to be different stages and material transport mechanisms associated with this process [57].

2.4.4 Liquid phase sintering

Several systems like super-alloys, tool steels, WHA, bronzes, etc. are sintered at a temperature where one of the phases forms a liquid. The consolidation process is therefore termed as LPS. LPS refers to the sintering process wherein consolidation is done at a temperature exceeding the fusion point of the low melting constituent in a mixture of powders. Hence, as compared to solid-state sintering, compacts can be densified through LPS at a relatively lower temperature and/or in lesser time. Nearly 80% of sintering process involves the presence of liquid phase at one stage or other during consolidation [58]. Figure 2.7 is the schematic depiction of various stages of LPS involving two mixed powders.

FIGURE 2.5: W-Ni-Fe ternary isotherm [4]

FIGURE 2.6: Schematic diagram of solid-state sintering showing the formation of open pore and close pore during sintering

FIGURE 2.7: Schematic of the microstructure changes during liquid phase sintering facilitating grain growth and pore removal

FIGURE 2.8: A schematic diagram showing the particle fragmentation and rearrangement

The solid grains are sintered in solid state during heating. Various microstructure evolution pathways are possible depending on the solid-liquid solubility relationship. The common situation is that the solid is wet by the liquid. The newly formed liquid penetrates between the solid grains, dissolves the sinter bonds and rearranges the grain. The liquid also improves the transport rates responsible for grain coarsening and densification due to the solid solubility in the melt. Porosity results in solid vapor and solid-liquid interfaces.

Both these interfaces, in general, have higher energies associated with them as compared to the solid-solid interface. Consequently, during the sintering, there is a natural tendency for pore removal, while there is progressive microstructure coarsening and bonding to increase rigidity. Besides mixed powders, LPS is possible using alloy powders that partially melt to form a semi-solid structure.

This approach is used to sinter tool steels. In another variant, a transient liquid forms and dissolves into the solid over time. This is how mixed copper and tin powders are used to fabricate porous bronze bearings. Finally, there are systems where the solid and liquid are insoluble, such as W-Cu, so solid-skeleton sintering determines the densification rate. However, the most common form of LPS is persistent LPS.

FIGURE 2.9: Ideal phase diagram that gives solid solubility in the liquid with a low solubility of the liquid in the solid

2.4.5 Densification during sintering

To promote densification during sintering, phase diagram characteristics play an important role. Figure 2.9 shows an ideal phase diagram for LPS [59]. The key requirements are high melting point difference between the base (solid phase) and the additive (liquid forming phase), and no high temperature intermediate phase formation. To avoid compact swelling, the solubility of the solid in the liquid should be higher than that of the melt forming phase in the solid [60].

Figure 2.10 schematically shows the effect of the liquid content on densification [61]. Note that figure indicates the contribution of the solid-state densification prior to melt formation, which was not considered in the classical conceptualizing of LPS. The selective importance of each process depends on the quantity of the liquid and solubility.

In addition to the atomic mass transport mechanism operating in solid-state sintering, the capillary stress exerted by the wetting liquid on the solid (base) particles also acts to

FIGURE 2.10: A schematic of the overlapping events in LPS

induce densification (shrinkage) during LPS. The minimization of the interfacial liquid-vapor energy occurs through pore removal. This stage is termed as rearrangement stage. The compact linear shrinkage during the rearrangement stage is expressed as:

$$\frac{\Delta L}{L_0} = D^{-1} t^{1+y} \quad (2.1)$$

where,

t is sintering time, and

D is the particle diameter.

The time exponential (1+y) varies between 1.1 to 1.6, and accounts for changes in the viscosity and the capillary forces.

For rearrangement, a key requirement is that the melt must wet the solid phase. When the liquid forms in LPS, the microstructure consists of solid, liquid, and vapor. Liquid spreading on the solid replaces solid-vapor interfaces with liquid-solid and liquid vapor interfaces. The extent of wettability by the liquid is determined by the contact angle [58].

FIGURE 2.11: Schematic showing low and high contact angle

As shown in Figure 2.11, the contact angle defines the equilibrium between the solid-liquid (γ_{SL}), liquid-vapor (γ_{LV}), and solid-vapor (γ_{SV}) interfacial energies. In the horizontal plane, the contact angle is associated with the balance of three interfacial energies and can be expressed as:

$$\gamma_{SV} = \gamma_{SL} + \gamma_{LV} \cos \theta \quad (2.2)$$

A low-contact angle induces liquid spreading over the solid grains, providing a capillary attraction that helps densify the system. In practice, a broad range of capillary conditions exist, since the microstructure is composed of a range of grain sizes, grain shapes, pore sizes, and pore shapes, each with a different capillary condition. A wetting liquid moves to occupy the lowest energy configuration, so it preferentially flows to the smaller grains and pores. This gives rise to capillary stress-induced rearrangement which causes densification. A high contact angle indicates poor wetting, so the liquid retreats from the solid. This results in compact swelling and liquid exuding from pores. Thus, depending on the contact angle, liquid formation causes either densification or swelling. The magnitude of the capillary effect depends on the amount of liquid, particle size, and contact angle. In fact, full density can be achieved in the rearrangement stage alone if sufficient liquid phase forms. It is estimated that nearly 36 vol. % liquid phases are required to obtain a full density product via LPS [62] However, a large liquid content often leads to slumping and dimensional precision control problems during sintering.

FIGURE 2.12: Schematic showing large and small particles at the start of liquid phase sintering

2.4.6 Solution-precipitation process

Generally, there is always a powder size distribution in P/M compacts. The relatively smaller and/or more irregular powders owing to their higher energy preferentially dissolve in the melt (binder), provided they have solubility for the base. The difference in the solubility establishes a concentration gradient in the liquid, which acts as a driving force for material transport. The preferential dissolution of sharp edges and asperities results in more efficient packing of the grains and contributes to densification. As described earlier, the solubility of base in additive is more when the latter is in melt form. The smaller/irregular grains will go on dissolving in the matrix till the solubility limit is reached. Once the melt gets saturated in the base, a steady-state condition is attained, wherein the smaller grains dissolve in the binder and reprecipitate on to the larger grains. The solution-precipitation process is referred to as Ostwald ripening and contributes to densification through grain shape accommodation and microstructural coarsening [63].

FIGURE 2.13: Schematic showing reprecipitation of tungsten after liquid phase sintering

2.4.7 Densification mechanism during solution reprecipitation

Kingery [61] proposed a different mechanism to explain densification during solution-reprecipitation. He treated densification as occurring from the hydrostatic pressure applied at the interparticle contact because of the capillary action of the pores present at these particle junctions. Consequently, the solubility of the contact between grains is more than the free solid surfaces, which causes preferential dissolution of particles away from the contact region and reduces the center-to-center distance between the particles. Shrinkage curve was separated into two parts with constant time exponents. The rearrangement-governed shrinkage, $\frac{\Delta L}{L_0}$, is expressed

$$\frac{\Delta L}{L_0} \propto t^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (2.3)$$

Kingery's model is restricted to systems having complete wettability (zero contact angle) and assumes that densification occurs only as long as pores are present. The final stage of LPS is solid state controlled. Rate of densification is very slow in this stage because of the existence of a solid skeleton structure, which inhibits any further densification by rearrangement and limited densification is achieved through diffusion.

FIGURE 2.14: Schematic showing three mechanisms of grain shape accommodation in LPS (a) Contact flattening (b) Small grain dissolution (c) Solid state bonding for neck formation

Usually pores remain in the compact after rearrangement, especially since the typical liquid content is below the 30 vol.% needed to fill all voids on liquid formation. Solution-precipitation is the most important means to reach full density during LPS. Three mechanisms are envisioned as means to densify the structure.

1. Contact flattening
2. Dissolution of small grains
3. Solid state bonding

Contact flattening is the first mechanism and it is sketched in Figure 2.14. A compressive force at the grain contacts from the wetting liquid pulls the grains together. This capillary stress causes preferential dissolution of solid at the contact point with reprecipitation at regions away from the contact. Densification results from the grain center-to-center

motion [64]. The key step is solid diffusion in the liquid to areas away from the contact zone. For small grains, the contact zone stresses are quite large, so contact flattening tends to dominate LPS. However, contact flattening does not explain grain growth and the decrease in the number of grains. When grain growth is inhibited there is less grain shape accommodation [65, 66].

The second densification mechanism involves dissolution of small grains with reprecipitation on large grains. Small grains disappear while large grains grow and undergo shape accommodation. Diffusion in the liquid is the controlling transport mechanism, Figure 2.14. This mechanism does not involve shrinkage, so it is not an explanation for densification, except that grain shape accommodation enables better packing of the solid.

The third mechanism involves growth of the inter-grain contact by diffusion along the liquid wetted grain boundary, as indicated in figure 2.14. The contact zone enlarges to change the grain shape with simultaneous shrinkage of the grains. This does not involve grain coarsening, but it does require a cooperative redistribution process of the mass deposited where the grain boundary intersects the liquid [67, 68, 69].

These three mechanisms differ in the source of the solid and in the detailed transport path, but together they explain grain shape accommodation, grain growth, and densification. Grain growth occurs with densification. Indeed, grain size and density tend to follow a common trajectory for most LPS systems, showing more rapid grain growth as pores are eliminated. Although neck growth is initially active, it is not sufficient to explain all microstructure changes. On the other hand, contact flattening and small grain dissolution couple to fully explain the microstructure and density progression typical to LPS.

2.4.8 Neck growth

Neck growth by solution-reprecipitation occurs soon after newly formed liquid wets the grain boundaries. The resulting neck growth law is as follows:

$$\left(\frac{X}{G}\right)^6 = \frac{g_3 D_s \gamma_{SL} \Omega t}{G^3 RT} \quad (2.4)$$

Where,

X=neck diameter

G= grain diameter

g_3 = geometric constant near 160

D_S = temperature-dependent diffusivity of the solid in the liquid

C = solid concentration in the liquid

γ_{SL} = solid–liquid surface energy

Ω = atomic volume

t = sintering time

R = gas constant

T = absolute temperature

The amount of liquid does not significantly change the initial neck growth rate, as long as there is sufficient liquid to cover the neck. Neck growth models ignore the dihedral angle, so they are only useful for initial bonding. While there is a high porosity, grain growth is slow so a typical assumption is that neck growth occurs without a change in grain size [70].

Eventually, the neck size reaches a stable size dictated by the dihedral angle. For grains of size G with a bond of size X (shown in Figure 2.15), the equilibrium neck size depends on the dihedral angle φ as given by

$$X = G \sin\left(\frac{\varphi}{2}\right) \quad (2.5)$$

Where,

G = grain size

X = neck diameter

ϕ = dihedral angle

Once formed, the distributions in grain sizes, contact misorientation angles, and surface energy give a distribution to the neck sizes. The grain size distribution leads to large–small grain combinations. The grain boundary between the grains must be curved to preserve the dihedral angle; the curvature increases with the grain size ratio [71].

FIGURE 2.15: Schematic showing two spherical particles with grain diameter G forming bond of length X

FIGURE 2.16: Schematic showing coalescence during LPS of different size

Associated with initial neck growth is shrinkage and densification. As a first approximation, the sintering shrinkage $\frac{\Delta L}{L_0}$ is proportional to the neck size ratio $\frac{X}{G}$,

$$\frac{\Delta L}{L_0} = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{X}{G} \right)^2 \quad (2.6)$$

In LPS material with a dihedral angle of 60° the neck size ratio grows to a limiting value of $X/G = 0.5$, corresponding to a peak shrinkage of 6.25%. But at a dihedral angle of 23° , the corresponding shrinkage is just 1%. After the stable neck size ratio is formed, as dictated by the dihedral angle, X/G remains constant and further neck growth depends on grain growth [72, 73].

2.4.9 Coalescence

A wetting liquid induces particle contact due to an attractive capillary force. Amorphous particles will coalesce, since there is no grain boundary [74]. For crystalline solids, there is a 5–10% probability that a random grain contact will form with a low-angle grain boundary that favors coalescence. The driving force of coalescence is the grain boundary curvature.

FIGURE 2.17: Schematic showing radius of curvature of grain boundary depends on dihedral angle and the grain size ratio $\frac{G_1}{G_2}$

Coalescence occurs as grains of differing size come into contact, resulting in growth of a neck with a grain boundary, and then migration of the grain boundary through the smaller grain to form a single large grain (shown in Figure 2.16). The radius of curvature r of the grain boundary between contacting grains depends on the dihedral angle φ and the grain size ratio (G_1/G_2) (indicated in Figure 2.17). A large ratio induces a high curvature that aids rapid grain coalescence during LPS [75].

$$r = \cos\left(\frac{\varphi}{2}\right) \left[\frac{G_1 G_2}{G_1 - G_2} \right] \quad (2.7)$$

Large-small grain combinations naturally favor coalescence. Also, chemical gradients, where the solid grains have differing compositions, accelerate boundary motion and coalescence [76].

2.4.10 Mechanism of Coalescence

Four transport paths are possible (schematic in Figure 2.18):

1. grain boundary migration by solid-state diffusion,
2. grain boundary migration by diffusion across a thin liquid film on the boundary
3. solution-precipitation from the small grain to the adjacent large grain
4. grain rotation into a coincidence condition

Experimental evidence confirms grain boundary migration with a thin liquid layer. Grain rotation is favored by high-liquid contents because there are fewer bonds to retard rotation.

FIGURE 2.18: Schematic showing the mechanisms of coalescence during LPS (a) Solid state grain boundary motion (b) Liquid film migration (c) solution reprecipitation (d) small grain rotation to a lattice coincidence orientation where there is no grain boundary

At high-solid contents, boundary migration is the typical mechanism. As the small grains are absorbed, coalescence decreases [77, 78, 79, 80, 81].

2.4.11 Grain Coarsening

During this stage, grain coalescence contributes to grain growth. In general, grain coarsening follows a power law with time,

$$G_t^n - G_0^n = Kt \quad (2.8)$$

where, G_0 is the initial grain size after the liquid formation transients, G_t is the grain size after isothermal hold for time t , and K is the growth rate constant which depends on material parameters and related to transport mechanism. Values of n near 3 indicate the mean grain volume increases linearly with time and the number of grains decreases with inverse time [58]. However, for instances where the grains are flat faced, solution-reprecipitation is limited by a low population of interfacial sites and n is near 2. A range of microstructures is possible through LPS, which depends on processing variables such as powder size, alloy composition, sintering temperature and time. Optimization of the microstructure in LPS is critical, as it influences the properties of sintered compacts. Upadhyaya [8] has recently shown that microstructural attributes influence the macrostructure, i.e. the compact structural rigidity and its dimensional precision.

2.4.12 Pore filling

Pore filling by liquid preferentially starts at a localized region in the compact and spreads during LPS [82]. Small pores fill first, since they have the highest capillary attraction for the wetting liquid. High-green density regions correspond to smaller pores, so pore filling naturally favors the high green density regions [83]. The slower process of liquid flow into large pores is illustrated in Figure 2.19. When a large pore is surrounded by smaller grains, pore filling is delayed because the capillary forces retain the liquid in small channels. During prolonged sintering, grains growth reduces the capillary gradients and eventually reaches a favorable condition for liquid to flow into the pore [78, 84, 85]. This condition is described by the liquid meniscus radius at the pore-liquid-grain contact, r_m is given as:

$$r_m = \frac{G}{2} \left(\frac{1 - \cos \alpha}{\cos \alpha} \right) \quad (2.9)$$

where,

G is the grain diameter

α = angle from the grain center to the solid-liquid-vapor contact point.

Pore filling occurs when the pore size and meniscus radius are about the same and is favored by a low-contact angle. Grain growth usually follows a cube-root dependence on time, so the filling of large pores can be delayed for some time. However, trapped gas in the pores will retard densification [86].

A pore larger than the grain size is initially stable, but subsequently grain growth reaches a critical condition where liquid flows into the pore, leading to liquid-filled lakes in the final microstructure. The critical condition depends on the pore size d_P , grain size G , liquid meniscus radius r_m for the liquid, and angle α between the meniscus contact and the line connecting grain centers. Grain growth during solution-precipitation eventually triggers large pore filling.

2.4.13 Research work related to sintering of heavy alloy

The sintered properties of WHA exhibit a complex dependence on the independent parameters such as particle size; matrix composition; sintering time, temperature and atmosphere; heating/cooling rate; and post-sintering heat-treatment. German *et al.* [87] correlated the strength and ductility of W-Ni-Fe heavy alloys with the microstructure and found that ductility of the alloys continuously decreases with increasing tungsten

FIGURE 2.19: Schematic showing pore filling in LPS

content and an optimal combination of strength and ductility is achieved at about 93% tungsten. Belhadjhamida and German [88] too confirmed the decrease in ductility with increasing tungsten content. However, they found that the strength of W–Ni–Fe alloy increases with an increasing tungsten content and attains a maximum at about 85 vol.% (93 wt.%) tungsten. Besides tungsten powder size and distribution, the properties of W–Ni–Fe alloys are also influenced by sintering time and temperature. Bourguignon and German [89] reported lower strength and higher ductility of 93W–4.9Ni–2.1Fe alloy liquid phase sintered at higher temperature. The strength decreased from 924 to 899 MPa and the ductility increased from 14% to 27% when the sintering temperature was increased from 1465 to 1580 °C. This was attributed to the rate of tungsten grain growth, which results in proportionately higher fraction of matrix phase between the grains. In yet another study, Bose *et al.* [90] reported similar effect of temperature on strength and ductility of liquid phase sintered 90W–7Ni–3Fe system. Chicardi *et al.* [91] studied the effect of sintering time on the microstructure and mechanical properties of WHA. They reported that increasing sintering time also resulted in microstructural coarsening, which deteriorated the mechanical properties. Consequently, the tensile strength and elongation in WHA was usually found to be highest for shorter sintering times (30–90 min). Conventional sintering of W–Ni–Fe alloys results in grain growth and long sintering time results in precipitation of brittle intermetallic phases. To avoid this, the matrix composition is restricted to an optimal nickel to iron ratio of 7:3. Microwave sintering of W–Ni–Fe composition

were first studied by Upadhyaya *et al.* [6]., They investigated the sintering response of a 92.5W-7.5(Ni-Fe) alloy - with a non-optimal matrix composition-consolidated through microwaves and compared its densification, microstructure and mechanical properties vis a vis conventionally sintered compact.

Taking into consideration the slow heating rate (5 °C/min) in conventional furnace, there was about 75% reduction in the process time of W-Ni-Fe compacts in microwave furnace. This can be attributed to the fact that in microwaves the sample per se heats up and acts as the source of heat. Both conventional as well as microwave sintered samples attained >98.5% density. Sintering-time compression through microwaves restricts tungsten grain growth.

Satyanarayana *et al.* [92] mixed the powder in high energy planetary ball mill with the WHA ball as milling media and ball to powder ratio 2:1 for 24 hrs. The milled powders compacted by using cold iso-static press at a pressure of 200MPa for 2min dwell time to rod of diameter 40mm and length 100mm. LPS was carried out in continuous pusher type electrical heating furnace at 1460 °C for WHA 1 and 1410 °C for WHA 2 as sintering temperature for nearly 2h under hydrogen atmosphere followed by post sintering operation of vacuum annealing at 1100 °C for 5h to reduce amount of hydrogen entrapped at sintering and segregation of intermetallics formed while sintering at grain boundaries and then it was cold swaged to 30% reduction in diameter

2.5 Mechanical property of WHA

Typically, depleted uranium alloys, U-0.75Ti, were used as penetrator materials in cannon-fired KE projectiles. The high density of these materials permits the penetrator of these projectiles to deliver a large amount of kinetic energy upon the small presented area and efficient penetration through the armour protection. Due to dust generation of depleted uranium during usage leading to health hazards and environmental pollution, an alternate material of similar property is being explored. Comparing the limit velocity and density, WHA appears to be one of the potential candidates [8].

2.5.1 Mushrooming effect

Deformation of penetrator occur at tremendously high strain rates permitting very little time for the conduction and dissipation of the heat being generated. This results in an

FIGURE 2.20: Penetrator deformation behavior of (a) Depleted Uranium and (b) WHA penetrator

adiabatic heating condition which causes substantial plastic deformation at the penetrator head. Under these conditions, thermal softening of the penetrator material due to its rising temperature competes with the material strain and strain-rate hardening response. The deformation results in a “mushrooming effect” (shown in Figure 2.20) which causes an increase in penetrator head diameter and poor performance [93].

WHA develop “mushroomed heads” during penetration due to delayed onset of shear stress localization. Because of increased head diameter, a sizable fraction of the kinetic energy gets expended resulting in poor penetration. It is desired to promote adiabatic shear banding in small localized regions at a higher strain to further the penetration performance. As a result, the extensive deformation is localized long the shearing direction. Lankford *et al.* [94] showed shear banding in a liquid phase sintered 90W–7Ni–3Fe alloy at 5400 s^{-1} and Bose *et al.* [90] correlated shear banding and the mechanical working of the WHA. A contiguous microstructure containing a lot of W/W interface impedes the shear band formation which imply lowering the tungsten content enhances the shear band formation but at the cost of density. As WHA has wide application other mechanical properties like tensile strength, transverse rupture strength, bulk hardness etc. are also important. A list of these properties of different composition, heating modes and sintering parameter have been tabulated in table.

In general, with increasing tungsten content (in the range of 88-94 wt. % tungsten), the ultimate tensile strength, yield strength, and hardness of the material tends to increase

while the elongation of the alloy decreases. In some special grades the tungsten content can be as high as 98 wt.%. However, increasing the tungsten content above 94 weight percent can often result in a decrease in ductility and also ultimate tensile strength as the failure of the WHA is then dictated more by the microstructural characteristics of the two-phase composite (a drastic increase in contiguity). Thus, it can be said that the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of WHA exhibits a maximum and then drops off with increasing volume fraction of tungsten while the ductility tends to show a continuous drop. For example, maintaining the same Ni:Fe ratio of 8:2, but changing the tungsten content from 90 to 95 to 98 (wt.%), the UTS changes from 925 to 955 to 708 MPa, respectively while the elongation continually decreases from 36% to 17% to 1.5%, respectively.

Chapter 3

Materials and Methods

3.1 Materials

W-powder (grade: M55), supplied by Osram Sylvania (Towanda, PA, USA) was prepared by reduction and has rounded shape with an average of 6 *μm* diameter. The nickel powder (grade:123), prepared by carbonyl process, was supplied by INCO. The iron powder (grade: 180/2.6), prepared by water atomization process, was supplied by Pometon.

3.2 Powder Characterization

As received powders were characterised for particle size, particle size distribution, morphology, flow rate and apparent density measurement.

3.2.1 Particle Size and its distribution

A laser scattering analyser (Model: Economy, laser Klasse 1; supplier Fritsch, Germany) was used for measuring the particle size of the powders. The powders were suspended in distill water media with 10% sodium meta-phosphate. The laser scattered after interaction of particle were detected by strategically placed detectors.

TABLE 3.1: Particle size distribution of elemental powder

	W	Ni	Fe
D ₁₀	2.2	3.6	1.6
D ₅₀	4.6	12.1	7.6
D ₉₀	6.5	32.4	19.2

FIGURE 3.1: Micrograph of (a) Tungsten powder (b) Iron powder (c) Nickel powder

3.2.2 Particle shape

The particle morphology and shape of the powders was obtained using JEOL, JSM-7100F scanning electron microscope. Figure 3.1 shows the morphology of the powders used for the present work.

3.3 Sample preparation

Samples of WHA with a different volume percentage of the matrix was prepared with constant 7Ni:3Fe ratio. The required composition was obtained by blending the elemental powders in the requisite proportion. Powders were weighted to the accuracy of 0.001 g using an electronic balance supplied by Mettler Toledo, AE 200, USA. The balance was calibrated using the series of standard weights. The powders were blended in turbula mixer (Model: T2C Nr. 921266, Supplier: - Bachofen AG, Switzerland) for 2 hours. The resultant mixture was a homogeneously mixed powder.

Theoretical density of the alloy was calculated using the inverse rule of mixing. The theoretical density is expressed as follows:

$$\frac{1}{\rho_{th}} = \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} \frac{w_i}{\rho_i} \quad (3.1)$$

where,

ρ_{th} is theoretical density,

FIGURE 3.2: Presence of porosity and blisters after the three-step cycle

n is the number of component in the alloy,

W_i is the weight fraction of i^{th} component in the alloy,

ρ_i is the density of i^{th} component

3.4 Compaction

Blended powders were compacted at 400 MPa pressure using an uniaxial hydraulic press (Apex construction Ltd., UK). Zinc stearate was used as a die wall lubricant to facilitate the compaction.

3.5 Sintering

Sintering of green samples was performed in the horizontal tubular furnace (model: OKAY 70T-4) supplied by Bysakh and Co., Kolkata. The furnace was heated to 1500 °C with an accuracy of ± 5 °C. Reducing atmosphere of H_2 (dew point $-35^\circ C$) was maintained with a flow rate of 0.5 litres per min.

3.6 Different sintering cycle

Three step sintering was used at 5 °C/min heating rate in a hydrogen atmosphere. The sintering temperature was set to 1500 °C for holding time of 60 min. Furnace cooling was adopted to avoid oxidation of the sintered samples. Visual inspection of the sintered sample shows the presence of porosity and blister on the surface (Figure 3.2).

Pre-sintering treatment at 1000 °C for 30 min was adopted to lower the presence of porosity before the melt formation at 1500 °C. Density measurement by Archimedes principle shows

FIGURE 3.3: Absence of porosity and blister after adopting the pre-sintering treatment at 1000 °C for 30 min.

FIGURE 3.4: Sintering profile of a) Three step sintering b) sintering profile with pre-sintering treatment

the densification of 99.3% of theoretical density (Figure 3.3). Sintering cycle of both the process are shown in Figure 3.4.

3.7 Density measurement

Density measurements of the samples was carried out using Archimedes principle. Initially, the weight of the samples was taken in air then samples were immersed in pure distilled water and weights were taken in water. An analytical balance was used for all the measurements. The density was calculated using the following equation:

$$\rho_s = \frac{W_a}{(W_a - W_l)} \quad (3.2)$$

where,

ρ_s is the relative density of sample,

W_a is the weight of sample in air,

W_l is the weight of sample in water

Densification parameter (φ_d), is another quantitative way to describe the densification and is defined as the ratio of change in density in green sample to the maximum possible density change.

$$\varphi_d = \frac{(\rho_s - \rho_g)}{(\rho_{th} - \rho_g)} \quad (3.3)$$

where,

ρ_s is the sintered density of sample,

ρ_g is the green density of sample,

ρ_{th} is the theoretical density of sample.

It normalises the variable density in green sample which the prime advantage of using this parameter.

3.8 Metallographic Sample Preparation

Metallography is the study of the structure of metals and of metal alloys through the examination of specimens with a metallurgical microscope. The structures observed in the microscope are often recorded photographically.

3.8.1 Sample Selection

The decision on where to remove a sample from an object and how large the sample should be made so that the most information is obtained from the smallest possible sample. However, the sample size must be large enough so that the information obtained is representative of the entire sample. The location of the sample is critical in reconstructing the object's production history. Other than grains, metals and alloys frequently contain features. Pores (from the evolution of gases and the formation of bubbles in liquid metal as it solidifies in a mould); non-metallic inclusions such as oxide or sulphide particles or bits of slag in the metal; fissures or other flaws that may occur when the metal shrinks and cracks upon cooling; surface and internal corrosion products, and so on are examples of such features. All of these characteristics have meaning and must be observed and recorded. For each feature, the shape, size, colour (in plane polarised light or with crossed polars), and distribution are typically recorded. Some features, such as voids, cracks,

TABLE 3.2: Metallographic sample preparation

Abrasive	Lubricant	Speed	Time
220 grit	Water	100 rpm	Until Plane
500 grit	Water	100 rpm	1 minute
1200 grit	Water	100 rpm	1 minute
500 grit	Water	100 rpm	1 minute
1 μm alumina	Water	100 rpm	1 min
0.05 μm acidic alumina	10% Diluted etchant of 15 ml HNO ₃ , 3 ml HF (40%), 80 ml water	100 rpm	1 min

non-metallic inclusions, and corrosion products, are frequently visible upon microscopic examination of the highly polished surface of the metal sample. This is referred to as an examination of the metal in its as-polished state. However, before microscopic examination can begin, the metallographer must etch the metal and subject it to corrosive attack by a chosen reagent to reveal the grain structure. Examining the metal in its etched state is what this is known as. The sample has been polished and mounted in epoxy resin in accordance with the table 3.2.

During rough polishing, the preparation of tungsten can result in a layer of surface deformation. Prior to final polishing, this layer can be removed by lightly etching the surface with Murakami's reagent. To achieve recognisable image contrast on the sample surface is the fundamental goal of exhibit microstructure of material. The mechanism of the traditional method of etching is caused by the various phases' or grain boundaries' varying rates of corrosion to produce a contrast sample surface.

3.9 Matrix volume optimisation

It is well established that the fraction of matrix content plays a vital role in deciding the dimensional stability of the sintered sample. Hence, to optimise the fraction of matrix in the pressure-less conventional sintering, various compositions were investigated. The percentage of 7Ni:3Fe was varied from 2% to 20% of total weight. These samples were sintered using sintering cycle with pre-sintering. Green density was calculated using the conventional method as the sample is axisymmetric. Sintered density was measured using Mettler Toledo (Model No. H31AR) density measurement kit working on Archimedes' principle. The sample was sectioned using a diamond precision saw and was polished using series of emery papers (200-1200 grit size) followed by alpha alumina (0.3 μm) for metallographic examination. Microstructures were obtained using scanning electron

microscope (JSM-6010LA) and stereological studies like connectivity, contiguity, dihedral angle and neck growths were performed on these micro-graphs.

3.10 Sintering time optimisation

Mechanical properties of WHA is significantly dependent on the microstructural parameter. Microstructure of WHA can be modified by changing the sintering time of the pressure-less procedure used, and an exhaustive microstructural and mechanical characterisation was performed.

3.11 Mechanical characterisation

3.11.1 Vickers Macro hardness

Vickers macro hardness of the polished samples was measured on Universal Hardness Testing Machine (Model: FH-10; Tinius-Olsen Ltd.). The indentation dwell time was pre-programmed for 10 s, and one kilogram of the load was applied. The diagonals of indent were measured, and hardness was calculated using the following equation:

$$VHN = 1.854 \times P / \left(\frac{d_1 + d_2}{2} \right)^2 \quad (3.4)$$

Where,

P is the load applied (in kgf),

d_1 and d_2 are the diagonals of indentation (in mm)

3.11.2 Vickers Microhardness

Instrumented Micro-Indentation supplied by CSM International was used to perform the microhardness test. Indents were made on W particle and the matrix phase. The load used for indentation was 50 grams in each case. A diamond pyramid indenter was used and, it was programmed to dwell for 10 s. The square shape indents were observed and used for the calculation of Vickers hardness. Average of five readings is reported.

3.11.3 Compression test

Compression tests were performed on the Electra Servo-electric Testing Machine by BISS. Cylindrical samples having length to diameter ratio as 1.5 were used (*diameter* = 5 mm and *height* = 7.5 mm). The experiments were conducted at different strain rate of 0.77 s⁻¹, 1.5 s⁻¹ and 2.3 s⁻¹.

3.11.4 Tensile test

The flat tensile specimen was prepared as per the MPIF 10 standards of P/M. The sintered tensile specimens were undergone tensile testing on 50 KN capacity universal tensile machine at different strain rates. Strain rate of 2.8×10⁻⁴ s⁻¹, 2.8×10⁻⁵ s⁻¹ and 0.14 s⁻¹ were chosen for the current investigation. The gauge length of each sample was 25 mm. After the tensile testing, micrographs of the fractured surface were taken using the Scanning electron microscope in secondary electron mode.

3.12 Electron Backscattered diffraction

In order to investigate the effect of orientation of W-grain on grain growth during sintering, an Electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) analysis was performed. The samples were polished using colloidal silica solution (particle size of 0.05 μm) in vibromet polisher for 8 hours. Electron microscope (Model: JEOL, JSM-7100F) equipped with field emission gun, and EBSD detector provided by Oxford (model: NordlysMax²) was used for EBSD analysis. Accelerating voltage of 20 KV and probe current of 5 nA was set to execute EBSD. EBSD map was acquired at step size of 0.3 μm and EBSD camera binning at 2 × 2.

3.13 Quantitative Metallography

3.13.1 Microstructure evolution

In quantitative metallography, the volume fraction of matrix was calculated by taking area fraction of matrix to the whole micrograph. The matrix and tungsten have two different contrast in Back scattered electron (BSE) mode of electron imaging. Threshold

was applied to separate these two different regions, and the image was made binary. Then the fraction of area occupied by the matrix is calculated. Volume fraction was calculated using the area fraction using the stereological approximations. All the image processing was done with the help of ImageJ software. ImageJ is a Java-based image processing program developed at LOCI, University of Wisconsin.

3.13.2 Contiguity of the microstructural surface

Contiguity is the ratio of tungsten-tungsten interfacial area to total interfacial area. The fraction of area calculation can be stereologically reduced to point fraction method. It can be measured by using the following equation:

$$C_{WW} = \frac{2N_{WW}}{N_{WM} + 2N_{WW}} \quad (3.5)$$

where,

N_{WW} is counts of tungsten/tungsten interfaces

N_{WM} is the counts of tungsten/matrix interfaces intercepted by an arbitrary line with unit length on the micrograph.

Contiguity ranges between 0 to 1, indicating “0” as no contact and “1” for contiguous structure.

3.13.3 Connectivity

It is a number of two-dimensional co-ordination number of W particle in microstructure. It represents a measure of rigidity and stability of microstructure. Connectivity less than 2 is known to slump during sintering.

3.13.4 Dihedral angle

Dihedral angle represents the ratio of solid-solid to solid-liquid interfacial energy in a liquid phase sintered microstructure. Similar to other microstructural parameters dihedral angle also depends on sintering time, temperature, Ni content of the binder phase.

Computational determination of dihedral angle

FIGURE 3.5: Representation of steps in image processing (a) typical WHA micrograph (b) segmentation of micrograph to different class (c) binary image (d) edge detection

FIGURE 3.6: (a) Graph showing detection of entrant corners (negative curvature values) and (b) determination of angle by fitting points near corner

Step 1: Secondary electron image was segmented using “Trainable Weka Segmentation”

Step 2: Segmented image was converted to binary image

Step 3: Perimeter of the binary image was plotted

Step 4: Points with change in curvature was determined using Wolfram Mathematica

Step 5: Tangents were drawn by fitting points before and after the point of inflection

Step 6: Angle between the tangents was determined (called dihedral angle)

Step 7: Average of all the dihedral angle is reported

Figure corresponding to each step is illustrated in Figure 3.5 and Figure 3.6

Note: Mathematica Code used for the above calculation is given in the appendix 1.

3.13.5 Grain size measurement

The grain size was calculated from the binary image obtained during the volume fraction calculation. A watershed operation was performed to separate the two particles by a pixel distance. The ferret diameter of each particle was measured.

Chapter 4

Results and Discussion

4.1 Experimental Results

4.1.1 Powder Characterization

The elemental powders were characterized for various property like flow rate of powders, apparent density of powder, particle size of powders etc. and has been listed in table 4.1. Flow rate, apparent density and tap density of the powders were measured with hall flow meter. Particle morphology was observed through scanning electron microscope (Figure 3.1)

TABLE 4.1: Characteristics of the as-received powders

Powders	W	Ni	Fe
Processing Route	Chemical Reduction	Carbonyl Process	Water Atomized
Powder morphology	irregular	Spiky	irregular
Flow rate (s/50 g)	Non-Flowing	Non-Flowing	5.5
Apparent density (% theoretical density)	31.7	28.06	45.72
Tap density (% theoretical density)	43.12	46.02	49.53
Powder Size (μm)			
D ₁₀	2.2	3.6	1.6
D ₅₀	4.6	12.1	7.6
D ₉₀	6.5	32.4	19.2

FIGURE 4.1: Micrograph of pre-sintered tungsten heavy alloy

4.2 Effect of presintering

As discussed earlier, a presintering at 1000 °C for an hour was given during sintering of WHA. To understand the effect of presintering on sample, it was cooled just after the presintering cycle and microstructural investigation was performed. Figure 4.1 shows the microstructure of sample after presintering, it clearly shows the removal of most of the porosity from the sample. Porosity further get reduced while heating till sintering temperature and melt formation. This effect aids to obtain the fully dense WHA.

4.3 Density and densification behavior

As described earlier, to obtain the optimum volume fraction of matrix for conventional sintering different fraction of binder content was added to the sample. Figure 4.2 shows the variations in green and sintered density in different alloys.

As the green density of each alloys are different so observation of extent of densification during sintering cannot be made just looking at the sintered density. A normalization of densification is required, to achieve the same a ratio of change in density observed and maximum change in density that can occur is taken. This ratio which characterize the densification behavior is known as densification parameter. Figure 4.3 shows the variation in densification parameter for different alloys and it clearly depicts the enhancement of densification with increasing matrix content. Although densification parameter shows the

FIGURE 4.2: Relative density of green compacts and sintered compacts vs matrix content

FIGURE 4.3: Densification parameter of WHA sintered sample with matrix content

FIGURE 4.4: Photos of the WHAs after sintering at 1500°C for 30 min with initial green porosity of $\sim 54\%$

better sinterability of 20% matrix content but it says nothing about the loss of dimensional stability of the sample.

4.4 Matrix fraction optimization

On visual inspection of the prepared sample, it can be easily concluded that sample 15% and 20% matrix content has lost the shape and slumped during the sintering. Figure 4.4 shows the photographs of the sintered sample which clearly showing 15% and 20% matrix content sample has lost the dimensional stability during sintering and slumped. With the help of this observation, it can be concluded that 15% and 20% matrix content in WHA will lead to distorted final product. To decipher the reason of slumping behavior it was sectioned and prepared for metallographic investigation along with the other sample.

4.5 Optical Micrographs

It can be observed that alloy with 2% and 5% matrix content has the presence of porosity in the microstructure. Presence of porosity in the alloy indicates the inadequate amount of melt formation during sintering. The visual inspection and microscopic analysis of these samples lead to a conclusion that optimum amount of matrix for W–Ni–Fe system in conventional sintering is 10% matrix content.

4.6 Stereological studies

4.6.1 Contiguity

Figure 4.6(a) shows the contiguity variation in 80W, 85W, 90W, 95W and 98W alloys with different Ni to Fe ratio sintered at 1500°C . Increase in contiguity with the decrease

FIGURE 4.5: Optical micrograph of (a) 98W-1.4Ni-0.6Fe (b) 95W-3.5Ni-1.5Fe (c) 90W-7Ni-3Fe (d) 85W-10.5Ni-4.5Fe and (e) 80W-14Ni-6Fe

FIGURE 4.6: Plot of (a) Contiguity and (b) Connectivity as a function of matrix content sintered at 1500 °C

in matrix content can be concluded from the diagram.

4.6.2 Connectivity

Connectivity greater than two during sintering forms a chain like structure. If connectivity is less than two during sintering then sample will slump during sintering. Figure 4.6(b) shows that variation of connectivity with matrix content measured on the sintered sample. Connectivity for 15% and 20% matrix content sample is 2.8 and 2.1 respectively, measured in slumped condition, which indicate that connectivity during sintering must have been less than 2 and that lead to slumping of the tungsten in the sample.

4.6.3 Dihedral angle

Figure 4.7 shows the effect of matrix content on the dihedral angle and it shows that for higher matrix content average dihedral angle is very at lower angle configuration. It also shows the dihedral angle get steeper beyond 10% matrix content. Sudden decrease in dihedral angle for slumped sample shows that structure during sintering must be unstable and will lead to distortion.

FIGURE 4.7: Variation of dihedral angle in WHA with matrix content sintered at 1500 °C

4.7 Effect of sintering time

Above study reveals that 90W–7Ni–3Fe is the most optimum composition for the W–Ni–Fe system. Sintering time has another major role in sintering. The effect of various isothermal sintering time was studied on the 90W–7Ni–3Fe.

4.7.1 Grain size distribution

Rapid grain growth of tungsten particle in WHA is very much known and large particle of tungsten is blamed for poor strength in heavy alloy system. A detailed study of growth with sintering time was very much needed. 90W–7Ni–3Fe was sintered for 5, 30, 60, 90, 120, 150 and 180 minutes Figure 4.8 shows the grain growth behavior of tungsten grain. It shows that grain growth starts rapidly initially and keep on growing but rate of growth decreases with time. As the sintering progress the tungsten particle get rounded with time due to Ostwald ripening. The variation of aspect ratio with sintering time is shown in Figure 4.9. Since smaller grain keep dissolving to get precipitated on large grain, the grain size distribution as a function of sintering time is presented in Figure 4.10. It can be observed that with time fraction of large grain keeps on increasing and the size of largest atom also keeps on increasing.

FIGURE 4.8: Plot of tungsten grain size vs sintering time at temperature 1500 °C

4.7.2 Dihedral angle

The mean dihedral angle keeps on increasing with sintering time indicating that coarsening due to coalescence is being dominated after thirty minutes sintering cycle.

4.7.3 3D Co-ordination number

With the known amount of fraction of solid and dihedral angle, 3D co-ordination number can be calculated with the proposed method given by German *et al.* [11]. It can be clearly observed that co-ordination no. remains almost constant between 8-10. 3D co-ordination no. of greater than or equal to 4 is desired for rigid solid skeleton or grain will settle and distortion in system will be observed.

4.7.4 Connectivity

Although derived the connectivity shows that connectivity should keep on increasing with time but in observation first increase and then decrease in connectivity was noticed.

FIGURE 4.9: Plot showing the variation of aspect ratio of tungsten grain with sintering time at 1500 °C

FIGURE 4.10: Plot showing the distribution of tungsten grain size with varying sintering time sintered at 1500 °C

FIGURE 4.11: Stereographic triangle, each color indicating an individual orientation

FIGURE 4.12: Inverse pole figure map of powder particle showing single orientation in each powder particle

4.8 EBSD

EBSD reveals the crystallographic orientation of the grain. Each color indicate the orientation of grain and it can be read through the stereographic triangle shown in Figure 4.11. EBSD of the clearly indicate the as received powder was of single crystal. There is no multiple grain present in each powder particle (Figure 4.12). Figure 4.13 shows the EBSD map of as sintered sample and it can be observed that each grain is having a single color which imply that each grain is single crystal with much larger grain size than initial powder particle. During solution reprecipitation the precipitate grow in the same orientation as of parent powder particle.

It is believed that smaller grain rotates to the extent that its orientation matches with the large particle. EBSD of as-sinter material was taken and all such cases has been shown in Figure 4.14. This is one of the reasons for rapid grain growth.

FIGURE 4.13: Inverse pole figure map of as sinter sample showing tungsten embedded in large grain of matrix

FIGURE 4.14: Inverse pole figure map of powder particle showing single orientation in each powder particle

FIGURE 4.15: Plot showing the compressive stress-strain curve at different strain rates

4.9 Mechanical behaviour

4.9.1 Effect of strain rate on Yield strength

Figure 4.15 shows the effect of strain rate, in compression mode, on the yield strength of W-7Ni-3Fe heavy alloy. It clearly depicts that yield strength is dependent on the strain rate. Figure 4.16 shows the variation of hardness in matrix, tungsten grain and a bulk material at different strains when the sample is compressed at strain rate of 0.025 s^{-1} .

Both the tensile and compressive mode shows that WHA system is a highly strain rate sensitive material. At slower strain rate yield strength is very low while at higher strain rate it shows high yield strength. To find the strain rate sensitivity of the W-7Ni-3Fe system, strain rate jump test was adopted and hence tensile test started at strain rate of 0.1 s^{-1} and after yield strain rate was changed to 0.001 s^{-1} and later after some strain, strain rate was increased to 1 s^{-1} . The same has been plotted in Figure 4.18

FIGURE 4.16: Plot of hardness variation at different strain when compressed at strain rate of 0.025 s^{-1}

FIGURE 4.17: Plot showing the tensile stress-strain curve at different strain rate

FIGURE 4.18: Plot showing the strain rate jump test in tensile mode showing the strain rate jump from $0.1s^{-1}$ to $0.001 s^{-1}$ and finally to $1 s^{-1}$

FIGURE 4.19: Fractograph showing the secondary crack in W grain and W/W debonding

FIGURE 4.20: Fractograph of WHA showing the W/M debonding failure

FIGURE 4.21: Fractograph of WHA showing the matrix tearing as one of failure mechanism

4.10 Fractography

The four possible fracture paths for heavy alloys are (1) Failure of matrix (2) Tungsten cleavage (3) Failure of W-W bond and (4) Delamination of tungsten-matrix bond. During Tensile testing, W-W bond separation is observed on the surface of alloy. The fracture originates from matrix and it propagates through matrix. The resistance by matrix, against crack propagation, decreases as tensile force increased due to work hardening. The amount of W-W grain separation, observed in Figure 4.19, is fairly large than other mode of failure. The fraction of different mode of failure is dependent on the amount of tungsten. The higher the amount of cleavage in tungsten grain, the higher the ductility and tensile strength of the material. The intergranular fracture was observed in the tungsten grain. Tungsten matrix interfacial failure was also evident at many places as shown in Figure 4.20 Tungsten-matrix interface was observed to have ductile dimple rupture (Figure 4.21). Due to low constraint provided by neighbor tungsten grain, matrix phase start deforming at lower stress level. A high amount of W-W grain debonding indicates that it is the weakest link for the deformation of heavy alloy. In close observation to tungsten-tungsten debonding, multiple shear line in matrix can be observed in matrix (Figure 4.21 and Figure 4.21). Rate sensitivity of WHA could be associated with the b.c.c. microstructure of the tungsten grain in contrast with the rate-insensitive f.c.c. microstructure of the matrix phase which surrounds the grains.

Chapter 5

Summary and Conclusions

The present study investigates the processing, microstructural Characterisation and mechanical behaviour of WHA. Property of WHA is dependent mostly dependent on the amount of matrix content and its microstructural attributes. Therefore, the first maximum amount of matrix was determined that W–Ni–Fe system can have for conventional sintering. The primary basis for rejection was chosen as either the presence of porosity in the sample or loss of dimensional stability. In investigation 90W-7Ni-3Fe was found to be fully dense and its microstructural attributes were also satisfactory. Once the optimum matrix content was achieved, another sintering parameter sintering time needed to be optimised. Sintering time plays a vital role in the grain growth of tungsten grain. Grain growth is very rapid in these systems due to melt formation, and W has a solubility in the melt. Solution reprecipitation act as both boon and banes, it enhances the microstructural attributes by rounding of tungsten grain, but at the same time, its grain size is also increasing rapidly. The 90W–7Ni–3Fe system was sintered for 5 minutes, 30 min, 60 min, 90 min, 120 min, 150 min and 180 min. Within 5 minutes of sintering time grain size increases 3-fold, and after 180 min it increases up to 7 times of its original size. In 5 min sintering time, some presence of porosity was observed, and from 30 minutes onward alloys were fully dense. So, a sintering time of 30 min was chosen as the optimum sintering. However, All the further study was done on 90W-7Ni-3Fe sintered for 30 min, microstructural attributes like connectivity, contiguity, dihedral angle and so forth, were also compared. EBSD of the microstructure reveals that each tungsten particle is a single crystal and it also tells that the growth of the particle is taking place in the same crystallographic orientation as the parent grain is present. It can also be concluded that during sintering along solid-state bonding and solution reprecipitation coalescence is also taking place rapidly. The EBSD analysis shows that tungsten grain rotates to match

the crystallographic orientation of parent or sink particle and it might enhance the grain growth process. Further mechanical behaviour of the sample studied via compression tests, tensile tests and strain rate jump test, hardness variation during compression and later Fractograph was studied obtained from tensile test It was observed that different mode of failure was simultaneously operative. Fractograph shows W/W debonding, W/matrix failure, failure of the matrix and brittle fracture of w particle was also evident.

In conclusion, the findings from present thesis work help in understanding the restriction on the amount of matrix content in conventional sintering along with difficulty to control the rapid grain growth. It discusses the phenomenology of the processing-microstructure-property interrelationship of WHA. Its understanding will help in further reducing the grain growth and improving the mechanical property.

Bibliography

- [1] W. Gurwell, “Solid-state sintering of tungsten heavy alloys,” *MATERIAL AND MANUFACTURING PROCESS*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 1115–1126, 1994.
- [2] R. German, A. Bose, and S. Mani, “Sintering time and atmosphere influences on the microstructure and mechanical properties of tungsten heavy alloys,” *Metallurgical Transactions A*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 211–219, 1992.
- [3] H. Okamoto and H. Okamoto, *Phase diagrams for binary alloys*, vol. 44. ASM international Materials Park, OH, 2000.
- [4] A. F. Guillermet and L. Östlund, “Experimental and theoretical study of the phase equilibria in the fe-ni-w system,” *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions A*, vol. 17, no. 10, pp. 1809–1823, 1986.
- [5] W. Liu, Q. Cai, Y. Ma, Q. Huang, and J. Zhang, “Fabrication of 93w–ni–fe alloy large-diameter rods by powder extrusion molding,” *International Journal of Refractory Metals and Hard Materials*, vol. 42, pp. 233–239, 2014.
- [6] A. Upadhyaya, S. Tiwari, and P. Mishra, “Microwave sintering of w–ni–fe alloy,” *Scripta Materialia*, vol. 56, no. 1, pp. 5–8, 2007.
- [7] C. Ren, Z. Z. Fang, M. Koopman, B. Butler, J. Paramore, and S. Middlemas, “Methods for improving ductility of tungsten-a review,” *International Journal of Refractory Metals and Hard Materials*, vol. 75, pp. 170–183, 2018.
- [8] A. Upadhyaya, “Processing strategy for consolidating tungsten heavy alloys for ordnance applications,” *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, vol. 67, no. 1-3, pp. 101–110, 2001.
- [9] Y. Şahin, “Recent progress in processing of tungsten heavy alloys,” *Journal of Powder Technology*, vol. 2014, 2014.

- [10] N. Senthilnathan, A. Raja Annamalai, and G. Venkatachalam, "Sintering of tungsten and tungsten heavy alloys of w-ni-fe and w-ni-cu: a review," *Transactions of the Indian Institute of Metals*, vol. 70, no. 5, pp. 1161–1176, 2017.
- [11] R. M. German, "Microstructure of the gravitationally settled region in a liquid-phase sintered dilute tungsten heavy alloy," *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions A*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 279–288, 1995.
- [12] A. Arora and V. Gopal Rao, "Tungsten heavy alloy for defence applications," *Materials Technology*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 210–215, 2004.
- [13] S. Park, S. Chung, J. Martin, J. L. Johnson, and R. M. German, "Master sintering curve for densification derived from a constitutive equation with consideration of grain growth: application to tungsten heavy alloys," *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions A*, vol. 39, no. 12, pp. 2941–2948, 2008.
- [14] R. Manikandan and A. Raja Annamalai, "Tungsten heavy alloys processing via microwave sintering, spark plasma sintering, and additive manufacturing: A review," *Processes*, vol. 10, no. 11, p. 2352, 2022.
- [15] A. Pathak, A. Panchal, T. Nandy, and A. Singh, "Ternary w-ni-fe tungsten heavy alloys: a first principles and experimental investigations," *International Journal of Refractory Metals and Hard Materials*, vol. 75, pp. 43–49, 2018.
- [16] M. Öveçoğlu, B. Özkal, and C. Suryanarayana, "A comparison of the sintering characteristics of ball-milled and attritor-milled w-ni-fe heavy alloy," *Journal of materials research*, vol. 11, no. 7, pp. 1673–1682, 1996.
- [17] A. Bose, C. A. Schuh, J. C. Tobia, N. Tuncer, N. M. Mykulowycz, A. Preston, A. C. Barbati, B. Kernan, M. A. Gibson, D. Krause, *et al.*, "Traditional and additive manufacturing of a new tungsten heavy alloy alternative," *International Journal of Refractory Metals and Hard Materials*, vol. 73, pp. 22–28, 2018.
- [18] A. Iveković, M. L. Montero-Sistiaga, K. Vanmeensel, J.-P. Kruth, and J. Vleugels, "Effect of processing parameters on microstructure and properties of tungsten heavy alloys fabricated by slm," *International Journal of Refractory Metals and Hard Materials*, vol. 82, pp. 23–30, 2019.
- [19] A. Macháčková, L. Krátká, R. Petrmichl, L. Kunčická, and R. Kocich, "Affecting structure characteristics of rotary swaged tungsten heavy alloy via variable deformation temperature," *Materials*, vol. 12, no. 24, p. 4200, 2019.

- [20] S. Zhou, Y.-J. Liang, Y. Zhu, R. Jian, B. Wang, Y. Xue, L. Wang, and F. Wang, “High entropy alloy: A promising matrix for high-performance tungsten heavy alloys,” *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, vol. 777, pp. 1184–1190, 2019.
- [21] H. Hafızoğlu and N. Durlu, “Effect of sintering temperature on the high strain rate-deformation of tungsten heavy alloys,” *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, vol. 121, pp. 44–54, 2018.
- [22] C. Smithells, “A new alloy of high density,” *Nature*, vol. 139, no. 3516, pp. 490–491, 1937.
- [23] G. Price, C. Smithells, and S. Williams, “Sintered alloys. part i. copper-nickel-tungsten alloys sintered with a liquid phase present,” *J. Inst. Metals*, vol. 62, pp. 239–264, 1938.
- [24] E. Green, D. Jones, and W. Pitkin, “Developments in high-density alloys,” in *Symp Powder Metall*, vol. 58, pp. 253–256, 1954.
- [25] O. Kubaschewski, *Iron—Binary phase diagrams*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2013.
- [26] H. Yoon, S. Lee, S.-J. Kang, and D. Yoon, “Effect of vacuum-treatment on mechanical properties of w-ni-fe heavy alloy,” *Journal of materials science*, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 1374–1380, 1983.
- [27] J. Posthill and D. Edmonds, “Matrix and interfacial precipitation in the w-ni-fe system,” *Metallurgical Transactions A*, vol. 17, no. 11, pp. 1921–1934, 1986.
- [28] I. Y. Dzykovich, R. Makarova, O. Teodorovich, and I. Frantsevich, “Distribution of elements during the formation of sintered alloys of the system w-ni-fe,” *Soviet Powder Metallurgy and Metal Ceramics*, vol. 4, no. 8, pp. 655–660, 1965.
- [29] R. Minakova, A. Pilyankevich, O. Teodorovich, and I. Frantsevich, “Nature of the strength of tungsten-nickel-iron alloys,” *Soviet Powder Metallurgy and Metal Ceramics*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 473–477, 1968.
- [30] V. Agababova and I. Chaporova, “Boundary of the monophasic γ -solid solution region in the ternary system w-ni-fe,” *Soviet Powder Metallurgy and Metal Ceramics*, vol. 8, no. 7, pp. 571–576, 1969.
- [31] E. G. Zukas and L. S. Levinson, “Matrix motion of low-volume matrix w-ni-fe composites sintered in a temperature gradient,” *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 863–869, 1975.

- [32] R. German and K. Churn, "Sintering atmosphere effects on the ductility of w-ni-fe heavy metals," *Metallurgical Transactions A*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 747–754, 1984.
- [33] A. Mondal, D. Agrawal, and A. Upadhyaya, "Microwave sintering of refractory metals/alloys: W, mo, re, w-cu, w-ni-cu and w-ni-fe alloys," *Journal of Microwave Power and Electromagnetic Energy*, vol. 44, no. 1, pp. 28–44, 2010.
- [34] W. Liu, Y. Ma, and J. Zhang, "Properties and microstructural evolution of w-ni-fe alloy via microwave sintering," *International Journal of Refractory Metals and Hard Materials*, vol. 35, pp. 138–142, 2012.
- [35] C. Zhou, J. Yi, and S. Luo, "Sintering high tungsten content w-ni-fe heavy alloys by microwave radiation," *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions A*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 455–463, 2014.
- [36] J. Clayton, "Dynamic plasticity and fracture in high density polycrystals: constitutive modeling and numerical simulation," *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, vol. 53, no. 2, pp. 261–301, 2005.
- [37] C. Kipphut, A. Bose, S. Farooq, and R. German, "Gravity and configurational energy induced microstructural changes in liquid phase sintering," *Metallurgical Transactions A*, vol. 19, no. 8, pp. 1905–1913, 1988.
- [38] K. Churn and R. German, "Fracture behavior of w-ni-fe heavy alloys," *Metallurgical Transactions A*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 331–338, 1984.
- [39] D. Edmonds and P. Jones, "Interfacial embrittlement in liquid-phase sintered tungsten heavy alloys," *Metallurgical Transactions A*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 289–295, 1979.
- [40] K. Ramesh and R. Coates, "Microstructural influences on the dynamic response of tungsten heavy alloys," *Metallurgical Transactions A*, vol. 23, no. 9, pp. 2625–2630, 1992.
- [41] I. S. Humail, F. Akhtar, S. J. Askari, M. Tufail, and X. Qu, "Tensile behavior change depending on the varying tungsten content of w–ni–fe alloys," *International Journal of Refractory Metals and hard materials*, vol. 25, no. 5-6, pp. 380–385, 2007.
- [42] S. H. Hong and H. J. Ryu, "Combination of mechanical alloying and two-stage sintering of a 93w–5.6 ni–1.4 fe tungsten heavy alloy," *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, vol. 344, no. 1-2, pp. 253–260, 2003.
- [43] A. Bose and R. German, "Sintering atmosphere effects on tensile properties of heavy alloys," *Metallurgical Transactions A*, vol. 19, no. 10, pp. 2467–2476, 1988.

- [44] J.-K. Park, S.-J. L. Kang, K. Y. Eun, and D. N. Yoon, "Microstructural change during liquid phase sintering of w-ni-fe alloy," *Metallurgical Transactions A*, vol. 20, no. 5, pp. 837–845, 1989.
- [45] E. Olevsky, R. German, and A. Upadhyaya, "Effect of gravity on dimensional change during sintering—ii. shape distortion," *Acta Materialia*, vol. 48, no. 5, pp. 1167–1180, 2000.
- [46] M. Zhou, R. Clifton, and A. Needleman, "Shear band formation in a w-ni-fe alloy under plate impact," tech. rep., BROWN UNIV PROVIDENCE RI DIV OF ENGINEERING, 1992.
- [47] T. Shawki and R. Clifton, "Shear band formation in thermal viscoplastic materials," *Mechanics of Materials*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 13–43, 1989.
- [48] E. Lassner and W.-D. Schubert, *Tungsten: properties, chemistry, technology of the elements, alloys, and chemical compounds*. Springer Science & Business Media, 1999.
- [49] K. Poulsen, S. Rubaek, and E. Langer, "A new intermetallic phase in the w-ni system," *Scripta Metallurgica*, vol. 8, no. 11, pp. 1297–1300, 1974.
- [50] B. Uhrenius, H. Pastor, and E. Pauty, "On the composition of fe-ni-co-wc-based cemented carbides," *International Journal of Refractory Metals and Hard Materials*, vol. 15, no. 1-3, pp. 139–149, 1997.
- [51] V. Srikanth and G. Upadhyaya, "Sintered properties of w, cr, ni heavy alloys," *Journal of the Less Common Metals*, vol. 120, no. 2, pp. 213–224, 1986.
- [52] V. Srikanth and G. Upadhyaya, "Effect of cold work and annealing on the mechanical properties of 90w-7 ni-3fe heavy alloy," *Journal of materials science letters*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 195–197, 1988.
- [53] J. Das, G. A. Rao, and S. Pabi, "Microstructure and mechanical properties of tungsten heavy alloys," *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, vol. 527, no. 29-30, pp. 7841–7847, 2010.
- [54] U. R. Kiran, S. Venkat, B. Rishikesh, V. Iyer, M. Sankaranarayana, and T. Nandy, "Effect of tungsten content on microstructure and mechanical properties of swaged tungsten heavy alloys," *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, vol. 582, pp. 389–396, 2013.

- [55] N. Senthilnathan, A. R. Annamalai, and G. Venkatachalam, "Microstructure and mechanical properties of spark plasma sintered tungsten heavy alloys," *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, vol. 710, pp. 66–73, 2018.
- [56] S. Caldwell, "Variation of ni/fe ratio in w-ni-fe alloys: a current perspective," *Tungsten & Tungsten Alloys-1992*, pp. 89–96, 1992.
- [57] D. L. Johnson, "Solid-state sintering," in *Concise Encyclopedia of Advanced Ceramic Materials*, pp. 454–458, Elsevier, 1991.
- [58] R. M. German, P. Suri, and S. J. Park, "Liquid phase sintering," *Journal of materials science*, vol. 44, no. 1, pp. 1–39, 2009.
- [59] R. German, "Phase diagrams in liquid phase sintering treatments," *JOM*, vol. 38, no. 8, pp. 26–29, 1986.
- [60] E. Crossin, J.-Y. Yao, and G. Schaffer, "Swelling during liquid phase sintering of al-mg-si-cu alloys," *Powder metallurgy*, vol. 50, no. 4, pp. 354–358, 2007.
- [61] W. Kingery and M. Narasimhan, "Densification during sintering in the presence of a liquid phase. ii. experimental," *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 307–310, 1959.
- [62] R. M. German, "Supersolidus liquid-phase sintering of prealloyed powders," *Metallurgical and Materials transactions A*, vol. 28, no. 7, pp. 1553–1567, 1997.
- [63] S. Park, R. M. German, J. Martin, J. Guo, and J. Johnson, "Densification behavior of tungsten heavy alloy based on master sintering curve concept," *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions A*, vol. 37, no. 9, pp. 2837–2848, 2006.
- [64] J. Marion, C. Hsueh, and A. Evans, "Liquid-phase sintering of ceramics," *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, vol. 70, no. 10, pp. 708–713, 1987.
- [65] W. Kaysser, M. Žvkovič, and G. Petzow, "Shape accommodation during grain growth in the presence of a liquid phase," *Journal of materials science*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 578–584, 1985.
- [66] D. N. Yoon and W. J. Huppmann, "Grain growth and densification during liquid phase sintering of w-ni," *Acta metallurgica*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 693–698, 1979.
- [67] G. Gessinger, H. Fischmeister, and H. Lukas, "A model for second-stage liquid-phase sintering with a partially wetting liquid," *Acta Metallurgica*, vol. 21, no. 5, pp. 715–724, 1973.

- [68] G. Gessinger and H. Fischmeister, "A modified model for the sintering of tungsten with nickel additions," *Journal of the Less Common Metals*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 129–141, 1972.
- [69] F. Swinkels and M. Ashby, "Role of surface redistribution in sintering by grain boundary transport," *Powder Metallurgy*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 1–6, 1980.
- [70] R. Makarova, O. Teodorovich, and I. Frantsevich, "The coalescence phenomenon in liquid-phase sintering in the systems tungsten-nickel-iron and tungsten-nickel-copper," *Soviet Powder Metallurgy and Metal Ceramics*, vol. 4, no. 7, pp. 554–559, 1965.
- [71] P. Chhillar, S. Sangal, and A. Upadhyaya, "Automated dihedral angle measurement in liquid phase sintered alloys," *International Journal of Materials Research*, vol. 95, no. 1, pp. 3–7, 2004.
- [72] S. Luyckx and A. Love, "The dependence of the contiguity of wc on co content and its independence from wc grain size in wc-co alloys," *International Journal of Refractory Metals and Hard Materials*, vol. 24, no. 1-2, pp. 75–79, 2006.
- [73] A. Shatov, S. Ponomarev, S. Firstov, and R. Warren, "The contiguity of carbide crystals of different shapes in cemented carbides," *International Journal of Refractory Metals and Hard Materials*, vol. 24, no. 1-2, pp. 61–74, 2006.
- [74] S.-C. Yang and R. M. German, "Grain growth kinetics in liquid-phase-sintered zinc oxide-barium oxide ceramics," *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, vol. 74, no. 12, pp. 3085–3090, 1991.
- [75] J. Powers and A. Glaeser, "Grain boundary migration in ceramics," *Interface Science*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 23–39, 1998.
- [76] S. Takajo, W. Kaysser, and G. Petzow, "Analysis of particle growth by coalescence during liquid phase sintering," *Acta Metallurgica*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 107–113, 1984.
- [77] G. Grathwohl and R. Warren, "The effect of cobalt content on the microstructure of liquid-phase sintered tac-co alloys," *Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 55–65, 1974.
- [78] T.-K. Kang and D. N. Yoon, "Coarsening of tungsten grains in liquid nickel-tungsten matrix," *Metallurgical Transactions A*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 433–438, 1978.

- [79] T. Courtney and J. Lee, "An analysis for estimating the probability of particle coalescence in liquid phase sintered systems," *Metallurgical Transactions A*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 943–947, 1980.
- [80] T. Courtney, "Densification and structural development in liquid phase sintering," *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions A*, vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 1065–1074, 1984.
- [81] L. Kozma, W. Huppmann, L. Bartha, and P. Mezei, "Initiation of directional grain growth during liquid-phase sintering of tungsten and nickel," *Powder Metallurgy*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 7–11, 1981.
- [82] D. Blaine, R. Bollina, S.-J. Park, and R. German, "Critical use of video-imaging to rationalize computer sintering simulation models," *Computers in industry*, vol. 56, no. 8-9, pp. 867–875, 2005.
- [83] Y. Kim, J. Park, and D. Yoon, "Liquid flow into the interior of w-ni-fe compacts during liquid phase sintering," *Int. J. Powder Metall. Powder Technol.:(United States)*, vol. 21, 1985.
- [84] J. Smith and J. Wood, "Elevated temperature compressive creep behavior of tungsten carbide-cobalt alloys," *Acta Metallurgica*, vol. 16, no. 10, pp. 1219–1226, 1968.
- [85] S.-J. L. Kang, K.-H. Kim, and D. N. Yoon, "Densification and shrinkage during liquid-phase sintering," *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, vol. 74, no. 2, pp. 425–427, 1991.
- [86] H.-H. Park, O.-J. Kwon, and D. N. Yoon, "The critical grain size for liquid flow into pores during liquid phase sintering," *Metallurgical Transactions A*, vol. 17, no. 11, pp. 1915–1919, 1986.
- [87] R. M. German, L. Bourguignon, and B. Rabin, "Microstructure limitations of high tungsten content heavy alloys," *Jom*, vol. 37, no. 8, pp. 36–39, 1985.
- [88] A. Belhadjhamida and R. German, "The processing of w-ni-mn alloys and their mechanical properties," *Advances in Powder Metallurgy & Particulate Materials-1993.*, vol. 2, pp. 227–239, 1993.
- [89] L. L. Bourguignon and R. German, "Sintering temperature effects on a tungsten heavy alloy," *International journal of powder metallurgy (1986)*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 115–121, 1988.

-
- [90] A. Bose, D. Sims, and R. German, “Test temperature and strain rate effects on the properties of a tungsten heavy alloy,” *Metallurgical Transactions A*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 487–494, 1988.
- [91] E. Chicardi, Y. Torres, J. Córdoba, M. J. Sayagués, J. Rodríguez, and F. Gotor, “Effect of sintering time on the microstructure and mechanical properties of (ti, ta)(c, n)-based cermets,” *International Journal of Refractory Metals and Hard Materials*, vol. 38, pp. 73–80, 2013.
- [92] P. Satyanarayana, R. Sankalingam, K. Sivaprasad, and A. Mukherjee, “Effect of composition on tensile and impact properties of tungsten-based heavy alloy,” in *Materials Science Forum*, vol. 863, pp. 40–44, Trans Tech Publ, 2016.
- [93] L. S. Magness Jr, “High strain rate deformation behaviors of kinetic energy penetrator materials during ballistic impact,” *Mechanics of materials*, vol. 17, no. 2-3, pp. 147–154, 1994.
- [94] J. Lankford, C. E. Anderson, and S. R. Bodner, “Fracture of tungsten heavy alloys under impulsive loading conditions,” *Journal of materials science letters*, vol. 7, no. 12, pp. 1355–1358, 1988.
- [95] E. G. Zukas, P. S. Rogers, and R. S. Rogers, “Spheroid growth by coalescence during liquid-phase sintering,” *International Journal of Materials Research*, vol. 67, no. 9, pp. 591–595, 1976.